

An Examination of the Implications of Transformative Leadership on the Perceptions Towards the Workplace

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Abstract: The purpose of this research is to assess the role of transformative leadership on perceptions of faculty members towards the workplace. Workplace perceptions refer to how individuals feel, believe, and behave in various aspects of their work, environment, and colleagues. This study seeks to differentiate the perceptions of faculty members working in private and government institutions/colleges in the Ghaziabad District, Uttar Pradesh. Satisfaction at the workplace and commitment towards the workplace are the two variables considered for the study. This study is based on survey data from 160 faculty members using the Likert Scale. A chi-square test was used to test the effect of transformational leadership on workplace perceptions. The correlation coefficient is used to explore the association between perceptions of faculty members. Responses were collected through subjective sampling and analysis. In line with prior research, transformative leadership is found to have a significant impact on satisfaction and commitment toward the workplace. It is revealed in this study, that transformative leadership (TL) has a significant effect on the perception of the workplace of faculty members working in both Private and Government Institutes. The study also examined the correlation between the faculty members of private and government institutes and presented an adverse association between the two. The results cannot be generalized to other parts of the state/country and elsewhere as they are limited to a specific region only due to different policies and mindsets of the employees that differ from place to place.

Keywords: commitment, perceptions, satisfaction, transformative leadership, workplace

1 INTRODUCTION

Good leadership by superiors and managers is one of the most critical factors in increasing employee engagement in firms. Leaders play a critical part in reaching the highest productivity of organizations since they manage to steer all employees to fulfil the organization's goals. Thus, to increase organizational efficiency, managers' and leaders' talents must be regularly and methodically developed. If a company wants to increase productivity, it should search for ways to develop leaders and encourage them to use acceptable leadership styles. Consequently, the present investigation seeks to examine the impact of transformative leadership on the perceptions of faculty members toward the workplace. Presently, we live in a time when change is unavoidable. Human resources are the most valuable and indispensable resources an organization has for running it smoothly, effectively, and efficiently. The success of an organization depends on the management and dedication of the hardworking and involved staff members. Workforce management depends largely on the level of leadership [1].

Leaders are interested in employees who are committed to the specific goals of their organization, which involves balancing the goals of the organization with the needs of its employees. Leadership creates connections that enable people and organizations to work together. Organizations are increasingly interested in understanding, developing, and improving the capabilities of their leaders [2]. Leaders are concerned with establishing in those they lead a willingness to fulfil the specific goals of their organization, which means achieving a balance between the goals of the organization and the needs of its employees. Leadership creates connections that enable individuals and organizations to work together. By integrating the learning environment as a mediator, the study opened a new line of inquiry between change leadership and employee art in organizational behaviour [3][4][5].

Conceptually, the mediating function of organizational learning business practices; changing culture between transformative leadership and creativity has been investigated, but it needs to be empirically proven. The study added value by vigorously investigating the impact of learning to manage the relationship between transformation leadership and employee art. In addition, the measurement was tested using a construction model by creating subtle communication flexibility with the help of a product identification method, which prefers successive retransmission. The goal of transformative leaders is to bring out the best in their workforce [6].

2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A successful organization is the result of leaders' ability to motivate employees to realize the vision and purpose of the organization. Simultaneously, as a result of the globalization period, the use of new technologies, particularly information technology, in dealing with an increasingly competitive market environment is required to develop more effective and efficient ways to increase firm efficiency. As a result, the Transformational process is seen in a range of leadership actions such as idealized control, inspirational encouragement, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration to improve firm performance.

Simultaneously, they will exert control over their organization by utilizing contemporary information technology to improve staff efficiency and the company's system [7]. Leadership is a critical component in the development of employee productivity in the workplace. A transformative leader is dependable in terms of organizational involvement and instilling in his or her followers a sense of shared purpose [8][9]. Transformational leaders influence followers' organizational commitment by encouraging critical thinking through new approaches, involving followers in decision-making processes, inspiring loyalty, and recognizing and appreciating the unique needs of each follower to develop their potential. A systematic review confirmed this view, showing that organizational commitment was higher among employees whose leaders encouraged participation in decision-making, emphasized consideration, and encouraged and cared about the growth of their followers. Transformational leaders can encourage their followers to become more involved in their work by forcing them to discover new ways to solve problems and difficulties and to identify with the needs of their followers. This results in an increased level of organizational commitment.

2.1 Transformational Leadership

Leadership is a process that must exist and be sustained in human life. People cannot live as a community in nature until they free themselves from dependence on others. Community requires leaders and guidance; a leader can establish a desired direction or purpose as well as determine how to achieve that direction or goal. Leadership involves focusing on common goals. Leaders focus their efforts on people working together to achieve a common goal. The emphasis on common goals has given leadership an ethical tone because it emphasizes the need for leaders to work together with followers to achieve a certain goal [10]. Charisma, the Individual Approach, Intellectual Stimulation, and Inspiration are the four dimensions of transformational leadership. A survey of transformational leaders' revealed that leaders frequently their way to demonstrate the functioning of the team as a model for leadership, as well as the support of all team members to merge team goals, and individual needs, and cultivate wisdom.

Fig. 1. Transformative Leadership [11]

2.2 Satisfaction at the workplace & Commitment towards the workplace-

Satisfaction with work is one of the foremost factors affecting one's work ethic [12]. As a result, organizational ethics experts are interested in accurately assessing job satisfaction and understanding its effects on employees in the workplace. Some well-known definitions of job satisfaction provide a clear understanding of it and are useful in research. Satisfaction with work is defined as the degree to which people are satisfied or dissatisfied with their work. It is an emotional response to a particular task and the environment and the human body at work. Job satisfaction, as a concept, also indicates how much is expected of a person's conceptual agreement. Job satisfaction is likely to be greater for those who see the limitations of compliments and contributions in their relationships with the rental business.

The level of happiness or satisfaction associated with work is referred to as the satisfaction of work. Employees will be more satisfied with the work if they have a positive attitude towards work issues such as the job itself, recognition, and opportunities for progress. A person who is satisfied with his job has positive views about it; a person who is dissatisfied with his work has a negative attitude toward it. Job satisfaction is defined as a positive or positive mood resulting from job exploration or work experience.

The level to which an organization provides resources, communication, reinforcement, and encouragement to employees to improve their well-being is called organizational well-being support. When individuals improve or change their behaviour, the "environment" around that change must be supportive; otherwise, change will either not occur or will be less likely to be sustainable. To fully support the improvement of workplace well-being, the organizational 'environment' must include policies and procedures, visible leadership and management support, role modelling, nudges, and default settings. An employee's impression of what the company values for his work contribution and concern plays a vital role in his well-being. It has been proven to offer significant benefits to both employees and companies [13]. Organizational support has a direct impact on national ethics, and leadership has a direct impact on organizational support. Therefore, enhancing service quality, leadership, organizational support, and national ethics as an organization must be addressed.

Although many studies have been conducted on this subject in the past, only a few have examined the combined influence of job satisfaction and organizational support among the faculty members employed in Private and Government Institutions. Also, no study is there to assess the evaluation of perceptions of the faculty members of Private and Government Institutions in a comparative way.

2.3 Research Objectives

- To analyze the impact of Transformative Leadership (TL) on perceptions towards the workplace.
- To identify the association between the perceptions towards the workplace between the faculty members of Private and Government Institutions.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design for the study is a thematic research design in which researchers find out the effect of transformative leadership on perception towards the workplace among the faculty members of Private and Government Institutions with a comparative study. In this study, two variables are considered job satisfaction and organizational support. The study is based on first-hand information with the help of a questionnaire.

The survey was conducted at selected Private and Government Institutions by the researcher. Data for this research study was collected through a structured questionnaire that was distributed to faculty members who were asked to complete the questionnaire. The data was collected on the Likert Scale and analyzed by using the Chi-Square test for hypothesis testing using MS EXCEL 2016 as the statistical tool while descriptive statistics were calculated and used in the interpretation of findings. The correlation coefficient is used to check the association between perceptions towards the workplace among faculty members of Private and Government Institutions.

The total sample size for the survey is 160 faculty members out of which 96 are from private and 64 are from government institutes of the District of Ghaziabad (Uttar Pradesh, India) is considered.

The collected data were analyzed using the Chi-Square test Hypothesis testing to assess the evaluation of Transformative Leadership on perceptions of faculty members towards the workplace.

3.1 Hypothesis for the Study

Research Objective 1: To analyze the impact of Transformative Leadership on perceptions towards the workplace.

H0. There is no significant impact of transformative leadership on perceptions towards the workplace.

H1. There is a significant impact of transformative leadership on perceptions towards the workplace.

Research Objective 2: To identify the association between the perceptions towards the workplace between the faculty members of Private and Government Institutions.

H0. There is no association between the perceptions towards the workplace between the faculty members of Private and Government Institutions.

H1. There is an association between the perceptions towards the workplace between the faculty members of Private and Government Institutions.

4 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

In Table 1, the distribution of respondents is given. In Table 2, the questionnaire and responses are presented. Chi-square and correlation results are presented in Table 3.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Parameter	Respondents	Private	Government	Total Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	29	20	49	31
	Female	67	44	111	69
Educational Qualification	Ph. D	39	31	70	44
	Postgraduate	57	33	90	56
Designation	Professors	4	1	5	3
	Associate Professor	10	8	18	11
	Assistant Professor	82	55	137	86

Table 2. Responses of statements on the 3-Point Likert Scale for faculty members of Private & Government Institutions

S. No.	Statements	Agree (%)		Neutral (%)		Disagree (%)	
		P	G	P	G	P	G
1	My director is available when I need support.	34	42	20	4	46	54
2	I am fairly evaluated on my work.	30	41	17	11	53	48
3	I have the flexibility to manage my workplace and personal life.	36	61	9	2	55	37
4	I receive recognition for doing good work.	43	35	6	19	51	46
5	My suggestion matters to my director.	48	49	11	12	41	39
6	I am willing to go above and beyond what is generally anticipated to assist this organization to succeed.	39	35	27	17	34	48
7	The organization holds a special place in my heart.	57	53	6	13	37	34
8	In my opinion, my ideals and the values of the organization are pretty similar.	53	40	12	20	35	40
9	I am deeply concerned about the sustainability of this organization.	47	24	21	11	32	65
10	I would be equally satisfied working for a different organization.	49	33	14	3	37	64

Abbreviations: P- Private Institutions, G- Government Institutions

Table 3. Findings of the Chi-Square test & correlation

Chi-Square test [Private Institutions]	
Chi-Square Value	61.095118244435
Degrees of Freedom	18
P Value	0.00000135965
Rows * Columns	10 * 3
Chi-Square test [Government Institutions]	
Chi-Square Value	80.921071747165
Degrees of Freedom	18
P Value	0.000000000591
Rows * Columns	10 * 3
Correlation is -0.1965	

Chi-Square Tabulated Value at 5% Level of Significance with Degrees of Freedom 18 is 28.869. The Chi-Square calculated value for faculty members of Private Institutions is 61.09. The Chi-Square calculated value for faculty members of Government Institutions is 80.92. Both the values are greater than the tabulated value of the Chi-Square test with degrees of freedom 18 which shows a significant impact of transformative leadership on the perception of faculty members towards the workplace.

Research Objective 1: To analyze the impact of Transformative Leadership on perceptions towards the workplace.

H₁ = Accepted, there is no significant impact of transformative leadership on perceptions towards the workplace.

Research Objective 2: To identify the association between the perceptions towards the workplace between the faculty members of Private and Government Institutions.

H₁ = Accepted, there is an association between the perceptions towards the workplace between the faculty members of Private and Government Institutions.

The association between the working faculty members of Private and Government Institutions is -0.1965 it is evident from the value that there is an adverse association between them.

5 FINDING AND CONCLUSIONS

As Table 3 revealed and relying on analysis and interpretation of data, the study discovered that transformative leadership has a substantial impact on faculty members' perceptions of the workplace. Additionally, the study showed an adverse association between the working capabilities of private and public institutions. The findings of this study are context specific (Table 1). The results revealed that private and government institutions/colleges of District Ghaziabad (Uttar Pradesh) are a female dominant sector with 69%. Prior research has demonstrated that these transformative leadership traits have direct connections to engagement dimensions both between and among individuals [14]. According to Conchie., (2013), transformational leadership encourages employees to be motivated at work [15].

A leader's support and the development of a setting that prioritizes learning from errors are examples of psychological safety that promote engagement. Engagement and organizational commitment have been demonstrated to be positively correlated with intellectual stimulation. In conclusion, these studies show that transformational leaders positively influence their workers' work engagement because they help them maintain a happy frame of mind. Recent research cast doubt on the definition, methods of assessment, and unequivocal benefits of transformative leadership for engagement. The beneficial aspects of transformational leadership elevate subjective motivation among employees, which brings out favourable psychological states. Employees who are more intrinsically motivated are more productive and efficient at their jobs. They are expected to become more receptive and productive in their work [16].

The purpose of this study is to analyse the impact of transformative leadership on perceptions of the faculty members toward their workplace. Job satisfaction and organizational support are the two variables considered for the study (Table 2). The faculty members who are working under transformative leaders are more satisfied at the workplace and are more supportive of the organization they are working for. The researchers also identified the correlation coefficient that there is an adverse association/correlation between the perceptions among the faculty members of private and government institutions/colleges. Employees who work for transformational leaders feel less worn out and more motivated since they are supported in fair and honest dealings with their co-workers. Employees that are intrinsically motivated are more likely to work hard at their employment, feel less fatigue, less emotional depletion, and have a greater desire to contribute to the business.

The faculty members working in government institutions/colleges are more flexible to manage their workplace and personal life as compared to the faculty members of private institutions/colleges (Table 2). The faculty members of private institutions/colleges are more concerned about the sustainability of their organization as compared to government institutions/college faculty members. 43% (percent) of the respondents of private institutions/colleges agree that they get recognition for their work by their leaders whereas, in the case of government institutions/colleges, 35% (percent) agree with the statement. There is a significant difference between the opinion that the ideals and the values of the organization are not similar between private and government institutions/colleges faculty members. Additionally, a business must transform in this rapidly changing digitized world by being well-informed about its personnel since a transformational leader may motivate others to produce unexpected or outstanding results. It grants employees control over particular jobs and, after training, the power to make decisions. Leaders increase the well-being and motivation level of a group through strong connections, and leadership can mobilize people into groups that can get work done. Workers can be inspired to develop better ways to accomplish a goal. This study suggests, it is necessary to create coaching and training programs for leaders to help them develop transformational leadership. These programs may include "programs for communication, motivation, and brainstorming, to equip staff with the tools they need to be more articulate and inspirational as well as think outside the box."

The study represented data from only the academicians working at District Ghaziabad of state Uttar Pradesh, India which may limit the study's generalizability it would have been advantageous to conduct this research across diverse sectors and in a different context. Some other features can also be considered for not generalizing the result of this study- the sample is collected to the specified region not covering the different parts of the country, differences in state policies and regulations of the private autonomous body registered under the University Grants Commission (UGC), employees mindsets, satisfaction differs from employee to employee, family dependency, job security, allowances, campus life, pay and perks, research and development, family benefits, leave policies, medical facilities, amenities or services, and self-made policies by private Higher Educational Institutions that are associate in day to day working as well as in contradiction to government regulations related with the employment of the academicians are some of the reasons that this study cannot be generalized for the other area of the country. Future research studies can be done by taking a larger sample size, different sampling methods, and different regions or longitudinal studies can also be done by considering other variables for the study.

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